

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by tetrabutylammonium tribromide

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Abstract : The oxidation of thirty-six monosubstituted benzaldehydes by tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB), in aqueous acetic acid solution, leads to the formation of the corresponding benzoic acids. The reaction is first order with respect to both TBATB and aldehydes. The reaction failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. There is no effect of tetrabutylammonium chloride ions on the reaction rate. The oxidation of [²H]benzaldehyde (PhCDO) indicated the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect. The effect of solvent composition indicated that the reaction rate increases with an increase in the polarity of the medium. The rates of oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzaldehydes showed excellent correlations in terms of Charton's triparametric LDR equation whereas the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted benzaldehydes correlated well with tetraparametric LDS equation. The oxidation of *para*-substituted benzaldehydes is more susceptible to the delocalization effect but the oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds displayed a greater dependence on the field effect. The positive value of η suggests the presence of an electron-deficient reaction center in the rate-determining step. The reaction is subjected to steric acceleration when *ortho*-substituents are present.

Keywords : Oxidation, benzaldehyde, correlation.

Tetraalkylammonium polyhalides are widely used as halogenating reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻³. Recently, tetrabutylammonium tribromide (TBATB) has been used for the bromination of some selected organic substrates⁴. There are, however, only a few reports regarding their use as oxidizing and brominating agents in synthetic chemistry⁵⁻⁷. These compounds are more suitable than molecular halogens because of their solid nature, ease of handling, stability, selectivity and excellent product yields. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic studies of the reactions of polyhalides and many reports (including TBATB) have already emanated from our laboratory⁸⁻¹⁰. There seems to be no report on the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by TBATB. In continuation of our earlier study, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of benzaldehyde and thirty-five monosubstituted benzaldehydes by TBATB in aqueous acetic acid as solvent. The major objective of this investigation was to study the structure-reactivity correlation for the substrate undergoing oxidation.

Experimental

Materials : The aldehydes were commercial products.

The liquid aldehydes were purified through their bisulfite addition compounds and distilling them, under nitrogen, just before use¹¹. The solid aldehydes were recrystallized from ethanol. TBATB was prepared and purified by the reported method¹. [²H]Benzaldehyde (PhCDO) was prepared by the reported method¹². Acetic acid (AcOH) was refluxed with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 6 h and fractionated¹³.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, freshly distilled benzaldehyde (5.25 g, 0.05 mol) and TBATB (4.82 g, 0.01 mol) were made up to 100 cm³ in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for *ca.* 6 h to ensure completion of the reaction. It was rendered alkaline with NaOH, filtered, and the filtrate evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in minimum quantity of conc. HCl and cooled in crushed ice to yield crude acid (2.0 g) which was recrystallized from hot water to produce pure benzoic acid (1.88 g, 94%, m.p. 121 °C).

To determine the stoichiometry, TBATB (2.41 g, 0.005 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.11 g, 0.001 mol) were made up to 100 cm³ in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water. The reaction

was allowed to stand for *ca.* 10 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. The residual TBATB was determined spectrophotometrically at 394 nm. Several terminations, with differently substituted benzaldehydes showed that the stoichiometry is 1 : 1.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the aldehyde ($\times 15$ or more) over TBATB. The solvent was a 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture (pH = 2.04), unless otherwise mentioned. The reactions were carried out at a constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and followed up to 80% reaction by monitoring the decrease in absorption due to TBATB at 394 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were computed from the linear ($r > 0.995$) least-squares plots of $\log [\text{TBATB}]$ versus time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that rate constants were producible within $\pm 3\%$.

Results

Stoichiometry : Oxidation of the aromatic aldehydes by TBATB results in the formation of the corresponding benzoic acids. Analyses of products and stoichiometric determinations indicate the following overall reaction.

Rate laws : The reaction was found to be first order with respect to the TBATB. The individual kinetic runs yielded a linear plot between $\log [\text{TBATB}]$ and time. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , is

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzaldehyde by TBATB at 308 K

$10^3[\text{TBATB}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[PhCHO] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	2.21
1.0	0.20	4.34
1.0	0.40	8.66
1.0	0.60	13.0
1.0	0.80	17.2
1.0	1.00	21.6
1.0	2.00	44.2
2.0	0.20	4.43
4.0	0.20	3.96
6.0	0.20	4.15
8.0	0.20	4.68
1.0	0.40 ^a	8.82 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

independent of initial concentration of TBATB. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in the concentration of aldehyde (Table 1). The order with respect to aldehyde is also one.

The rate constant of oxidation of thirty-six aromatic aldehydes were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated at 298 K (Table 2). The oxidation is not affected by an addition of tetrabutylammonium chloride (Table 3). The oxidation of benzaldehyde, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the reaction rate (Table 1). To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of [²H]benzaldehyde (PhCDO) was studied. The results (Table 2) showed the presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.52$ at 298 K). The rate of oxidation was determined in solvents containing different amounts of acetic acid and water. It was observed that the rate increased with an increase in the amount of water in the solvent mixture (Table 4). The rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde decreases with an increase in the concentration of potassium bromide but reaches a limiting value at $[\text{KBr}] \approx 0.16$ mol dm⁻³ (Table 5).

Discussion

A plot of $\log k_2$ at 288 K is linearly related to $\log k_2$ at 318 K ($r = 0.9993$, slope = 0.840 ± 0.008). The value of the isokinetic temperature is 705 ± 49 K. A linear isokinetic relationship is a necessary condition for the validity of linear free energy relationships¹⁴. It also implies that all the aldehydes for which the rates of oxidation are so correlated are oxidized by the same mechanism.

We have earlier⁸ carried out some conductivity measurements to determine the nature of TBATB in aqueous acetic acid solution. It was observed that acetic acid has very low conductivity. Addition of TBATB increases the conductivity of acetic acid. We measured the conductivity of TBATB in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid (100–30%) and water also. We found that the conductivity increases sharply as the water content is initially increased but reaches a limiting value in about 60% acetic acid-water mixture. Therefore, TBATB can be considered as an ionic compound, which exists under our reaction conditions as tetrabutylammonium and tribromide ions as eq. (2). No effect of added tetrabutylammonium ion also indicates that the equilibrium (2) lies far towards the right. Similar results

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by TBATB

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	3.35	8.45	21.6	51.3	66.9 ± 0.6	-80 ± 2	90.5 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -Me	7.18	17.4	43.2	99.2	64.4 ± 0.6	-82 ± 2	88.7 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -OMe	15.5	37.2	90.5	204	63.1 ± 0.5	-80 ± 2	86.8 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -F	4.43	11.1	28.7	69.4	67.5 ± 0.8	-75 ± 3	89.8 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.12	5.51	14.7	36.5	69.9 ± 0.7	-73 ± 2	91.5 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.17	0.49	1.47	4.09	78.4 ± 0.9	-64 ± 3	97.5 ± 0.8
<i>p</i> -CF ₃	0.47	1.32	3.72	9.81	74.7 ± 0.6	-69 ± 2	95.1 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -COOMe	0.65	1.78	4.94	12.7	73.1 ± 0.6	-72 ± 2	94.3 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -Br	2.08	5.40	14.4	35.8	69.9 ± 0.7	-73 ± 2	91.6 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -NHAc	7.67	18.5	46.6	108	64.9 ± 0.8	-80 ± 3	88.5 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -CN	0.29	0.84	2.43	6.57	76.8 ± 0.6	-66 ± 2	96.2 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -SMe	9.45	22.7	56.2	129	64.1 ± 0.7	-81 ± 2	88.0 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	72.9	162	378	765	57.6 ± 0.7	-86 ± 2	85.2 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -Me	5.67	14.2	35.4	81.2	65.3 ± 0.4	-81 ± 1	89.2 ± 0.3
<i>m</i> -OMe	5.48	13.6	34.1	78.8	65.4 ± 0.5	-81 ± 2	89.3 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -Cl	1.00	2.70	7.20	18.7	71.9 ± 0.6	-72 ± 2	93.3 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -Br	0.99	2.66	7.21	18.5	71.9 ± 0.7	-72 ± 2	93.3 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -F	1.21	3.35	9.12	23.6	70.4 ± 0.6	-74 ± 2	92.4 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.12	0.35	1.06	2.95	79.0 ± 0.9	-65 ± 3	98.3 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -CO ₂ Me	0.59	1.62	4.49	11.8	73.6 ± 0.7	-71 ± 2	94.6 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -CF ₃	0.41	1.14	3.22	8.71	75.1 ± 0.9	-69 ± 3	95.4 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -CN	0.21	0.61	1.78	5.02	78.1 ± 0.9	-64 ± 3	97.0 ± 0.7
<i>m</i> -SMe	3.87	9.74	24.6	58.1	66.4 ± 0.5	-80 ± 2	90.0 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -NHAc	3.48	8.81	22.4	53.2	66.8 ± 0.5	-79 ± 2	90.4 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -Me	25.8	58.4	126	270	56.9 ± 0.4	-97 ± 1	85.7 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -OMe	22.7	52.6	115	235	56.8 ± 0.3	-98 ± 1	86.0 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.32	0.93	2.46	6.30	72.9 ± 0.2	-78 ± 1	96.0 ± 0.1
<i>o</i> -COOMe	2.22	5.77	13.9	32.2	65.2 ± 0.1	-89 ± 1	91.5 ± 0.1
<i>o</i> -NHAc	32.2	73.0	150	296	53.6 ± 0.4	-107 ± 1	85.3 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -Cl	5.74	14.4	32.9	71.6	61.4 ± 0.3	-94 ± 1	89.3 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -Br	7.38	18.3	40.6	86.7	60.1 ± 0.4	-96 ± 1	88.7 ± 0.5
<i>o</i> -I	11.7	29.3	62.4	135	59.1 ± 0.7	-96 ± 3	87.6 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -CN	0.65	1.83	4.68	11.5	70.3 ± 0.2	-81 ± 1	94.4 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -SMe	30.9	70.3	145	29.6	54.0 ± 0.4	-106 ± 1	85.4 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -F	3.63	9.47	22.7	51.5	64.7 ± 0.1	-86 ± 1	90.3 ± 0.1
<i>o</i> -CF ₃	4.50	11.4	25.2	54.7	60.6 ± 0.5	-99 ± 2	89.3 ± 0.4
PhCDO	0.58	1.53	4.07	9.92	69.7 ± 0.5	-84 ± 2	94.7 ± 0.4
k_H/k_D	5.78	5.52	5.31	5.17			

were obtained in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by TBATB⁸. Thus in the present reaction also the reactive oxidising species is the tribromide ion.

Tribromide ion is known to dissociate to bromine and bromide ion [eq. (3)] and the value of the dissociation constant has been reported¹⁵. The effect of addition of bromide ion (*cf.* Table 5) indicated that as the [Br⁻] increases, the concentration of bromine and its contribution

Table 3. Effect of tetrabutylammonium chloride ion on the rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde by TBATB

[TBATB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [benzaldehyde] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³,
Temp. = 308 K

10 ³ [TBACl]/mol dm ⁻³	0.00	0.5	1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0
10 ⁴ k _{obs} /s ⁻¹	21.6	20.8	22.3	20.0	22.6	23.1

Table 4. Dependence of rate on the concentration of benzaldehyde in solvents of different compositions

[TBATB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 308 K

at % AcOH (v/v)	25	40	50	60	72
10 ⁴ k ₂ (s ⁻¹)	108	42.1	21.6	10.8	3.85

Table 5. Effect of potassium bromide on the rate of oxidation of benzaldehyde by TBATB

[TBATB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [benzaldehyde] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³,
Temp. = 308 K

[KBr]/mol dm ⁻³	0.00	0.04	0.08	0.12	0.16	0.20	0.24
10 ⁴ k _{obs} /s ⁻¹	26.8	25.2	24.0	22.7	21.6	21.4	21.5

to the oxidation of benzaldehyde decrease and become almost negligible at [KBr] ≈ 0.16 mol dm⁻³. As a large excess (0.2 mol dm⁻³) of bromide ion has been added in present reaction, the oxidation due to bromine will be suppressed. Thus in the present reaction the reactive oxidising species is the tribromide ion.

The increase in the rate of oxidation with an increase in the polarity of the medium suggests that the transition state is more polar than the reactants. The solvent effect

was analysed using Grunwald-Winstein¹⁶ eq. (4).

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + mY \quad (4)$$

The plot of log k₂ versus Y is linear (r = 0.9997) with m = 0.78 ± 0.01. The value of m suggests that there is a considerable charge separation in the transition state of the rate-determining step.

The effect of substituents on reactivity has long been correlated with the Hammett equation¹⁷ or with dual substituent-parameter equations^{18,19}. In the late 1980s, Charton²⁰ introduced a triparametric LDR equation for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities.

$$\log k_2 = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + h \quad (5)$$

Here, h is the intercept term, σ₁ is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized (resonance) electrical effect parameter when active site electronic demand is minimal and σ_e represents the sensitivity of the substituent to changes in electronic demand by the active site. The latter two substituent parameters are related by eq. (6).

$$\sigma_D = \eta\sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (6)$$

where η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site and is given by η = R/D, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric LD equation. For *ortho*-substituted compounds, the LDR equation has been modified to the LDRS equation²⁰, to account for the steric effects.

Table 6. Temperature dependence for the reaction constants for the oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by TBATB

T/K	L	D	R	S	η	R ²	sd	ψ	P _D	P _S
<i>para</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.55	-1.98	-1.19	-	0.60	0.9989	0.029	0.04	56.1	-
298	-1.45	-1.89	-1.15	-	0.61	0.9989	0.027	0.04	56.6	-
308	-1.37	-1.81	-1.13	-	0.62	0.9990	0.026	0.03	56.9	-
318	-1.30	-1.72	-1.03	-	0.63	0.9990	0.024	0.03	56.9	-
<i>meta</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.92	-1.32	-1.03	-	0.78	0.9999	0.003	0.01	40.7	-
298	-1.83	-1.27	-0.92	-	0.72	0.9999	0.005	0.01	40.9	-
308	-1.57	-1.20	-0.83	-	0.69	0.9998	0.006	0.02	41.1	-
318	-1.47	-1.17	-0.75	-	0.63	0.9977	0.009	0.02	41.3	-
<i>ortho</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.85	-1.61	-1.29	1.15	0.80	0.9999	0.001	0.01	46.5	24.9
298	-1.73	-1.53	-1.18	1.10	0.77	0.9998	0.001	0.02	46.9	25.2
308	-1.66	-1.45	-1.09	0.99	0.75	0.9989	0.00	0.04	46.6	24.1
318	-1.59	-1.36	-0.98	0.91	0.72	0.9998	0.007	0.02	46.1	23.6

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